

Evolving Paradigms in Complex IVC Filter Retrieval: Navigating Beyond Conventional Techniques

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Abstract

The domain of inferior vena cava (IVC) filter retrieval is currently experiencing a paradigmatic shift, precipitated by significant advancements in procedural techniques and the advent of specialized retrieval instruments. This evolution has catalyzed the necessity for a critical reassessment of the criteria defining "complex" retrievals within the context of contemporary vascular interventional radiology. Historically, the procedural framework for IVC filter retrievals has been predominantly circumscribed to conventional methodologies, such as the snare and sheath or loop and snare techniques, which have been delineated as the sole recommended practices within the manufacturers' Instructions for Use (IFU). However, the advent of more sophisticated and versatile techniques heralds a departure from this traditionalist perspective, challenging the extant paradigms and proposing a redefinition of complexity in IVC filter retrieval.

This article examines the trajectory of evolution in IVC filter retrieval practices, with a focused discourse on the integration and efficacy of advanced methodologies that have recently emerged in the field. Among these innovative techniques are the loop-over-snare method, which leverages a loop mechanism to secure and retrieve the filter more effectively, especially in scenarios where conventional snaring proves ineffectual; the balloon inflation technique, utilizing a balloon catheter to facilitate the repositioning and subsequent retrieval of the filter; and the hangman technique, which employs a noose-like mechanism for the retrieval of filters situated in anatomically challenging positions or those that have become significantly endothelialized. Furthermore, this article delves into the utilization of endobronchial forceps for direct mechanical engagement and retrieval of IVC filters, a technique borrowed from thoracic surgery that has shown promising adaptability and success rates in vascular interventional radiology. Additionally, the deployment of the Phillips CAVA Clear system for the mechanical disruption of tissue in growth around the filter, thereby simplifying the retrieval process, is critically analyzed. The discourse extends to the exploration of purpose-built sheath systems, such as the Argon Medical Kodiak sheath, which are specifically designed to augment the efficacy and safety of

complex retrievals. Moreover, the utilization of filter inversion techniques, facilitated by large-bore sheaths such as the 20-22 French Medtronic Sentrant or Gore Dry Seal sheaths, represents a novel approach in managing retrievals deemed infeasible through traditional methods.

This review aims not only to delineate and appraise the aforementioned techniques but also to catalyze a reevaluation of what constitutes "complex" retrieval in the current landscape of IVC filter retrieval practices. By doing so, it endeavors to foster a more nuanced understanding and classification of retrieval complexities, thereby guiding the development of more effective, safer, and patient-centric procedural strategies. Through this scholarly endeavor, we advocate for an expanded methodological repertoire and a dynamic approach to procedural complexity, underpinned by empirical evidence and clinical pragmatism, to enhance patient outcomes in the realm of vascular interventional radiology.

Keywords: IVC Filter, Loop-Over-Snare, Kodiak, Cava Clear, Hang-Man, Forceps

1. Introduction

The landscape of interventional radiology has witnessed a remarkable evolution in the domain of inferior vena cava (IVC) filter retrievals, heralding a new era of procedural innovation and technical prowess.^[1] The impetus for this transformation has been the development and integration of diverse technical tools and the refinement of skill sets among practitioners, facilitating a paradigmatic shift in how complex retrievals are approached and executed^[2]. Historically, the procedural orthodoxy for IVC filter retrieval has been predominantly anchored in the utilization of standard techniques such as the loop and snare or the snare and sheath methods. These conventional methodologies have been explicitly delineated within the Instructions for Use (IFU) by filter manufacturers as the recommended approaches for retrieval, thus shaping the procedural norms within the field.

However, the clinical landscape is markedly dynamic, characterized by a continuous influx of complex cases where traditional retrieval methods may not suffice due to various complicating factors such as filter tilt, migration, embedding within the venous wall, or significant endothelialization.^[3] Such complexities necessitate a reevaluation of conventional strategies and the exploration of alternative, more versatile techniques capable of addressing the unique challenges presented by these difficult-to-retrieve filters. This article endeavors to delve into the vanguard of IVC

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filter retrieval techniques, showcasing the innovative approaches that have emerged on the periphery of traditional practices. These include, but are not limited to, the loop-over-snare method, which leverages a loop mechanism for enhanced control and retrieval efficacy; the balloon inflation technique, utilizing the strategic deployment of a balloon catheter to facilitate filter repositioning and retrieval; and the hangman technique, which employs a noose-like approach for engaging and extracting filters in challenging anatomical contexts. Additionally, the article examines the adoption of endobronchial forceps, a technique borrowed from thoracic surgery, for direct mechanical engagement with the filter, the Phillips CAVA Clear system designed for mechanical disruption of tissue ingrowth, and the deployment of purpose-built sheath systems such as the Argon Medical Kodiak sheath, tailored to augment the safety and effectiveness of complex retrievals. Furthermore, the discussion extends to innovative filter inversion techniques facilitated by large-bore sheaths, such as the 20-22 French Medtronic Centrant or Gore Dry Seal sheaths, offering a novel perspective on managing otherwise intractable retrieval scenarios. Through a comprehensive exploration of these advanced techniques, this article aims to illuminate the current state of IVC filter retrieval practices, providing insights into their application, benefits, and inherent challenges. By doing so, it seeks to foster a deeper understanding among clinicians and physicians of the evolving procedural repertoire available for managing complex IVC filter retrievals, thereby enhancing patient outcomes and advancing the field of interventional radiology. This narrative not only acknowledges the technical and clinical advancements but also underscores the necessity for ongoing innovation, interdisciplinary collaboration, and evidence-based practice in navigating the complexities of IVC filter retrieval in the contemporary clinical milieu.

2. Techniques Overview

3. Loop-Over-Snare Technique

The loop-over-snare technique in IVC filter retrieval is considered a transitional step beyond traditional snare technique that employs a creating a pre-formed loop utilizing a hooked catheter such as a SOS Omni flush to feed a .035 glide wire underneath the apex of the IVC filter to encircle the apex or the top portion of the IVC filter, thereby securing it for retrieval. ^[4]The guidewire is fed be in the curved catheter underneath the IVC filter apex and is navigated back up towards the insertion sheath where the end is snared and pulled back through the insertion sheet so that both ends of the guide wire are sticking out of the hemostatic valve of the insertion sheath creating a loop through the IVC filter. This allows for manipulation of the apex of the filter and gives a

transitional rail to advance the retrieval sheath down to the apex of the filter at which point the filter can be ingested into the retrieval sheath and removed. This method is particularly advantageous in scenarios where the filter is tilted, migrated, or embedded within the venous wall, making traditional snare approaches challenging. The loop provides a controlled and secure engagement with the filter, facilitating its alignment within the venous lumen for a safer and more efficient retrieval. This technique's success hinges on its ability to adapt to the varied anatomical and pathological presentations of complex filter placements, offering an elevated success rate when standard snare retrieval fails.

4. Balloon Inflation Technique

The balloon inflation technique involves the use of an angioplasty balloon catheter, which is advanced to the site of the filter and then inflated to either displace endothelialized tissue or to reposition the filter into a more favorable orientation for retrieval.^[5] This technique may be successful in situations where the filter has become endothelialized or is in an anatomically challenging position that precludes straightforward snaring. By altering the filter's position or disrupting its incorporation into the venous wall, the balloon inflation method can significantly enhance the feasibility of subsequent retrieval attempts, making it a tool in the armamentarium for retrieval cases. A caveat to this technique is that there is a risk introduced of bursting the balloon which could become incorporated within the filter interstices and become entangled. Caution should be used when employing the technique especially near the legs of the filter which have hooking mechanisms which can be sharp and are designed to anchor the IVC filter into the wall of the vena cava to prevent filter migration before intimal endothelialization occurs.

5. Hangman Technique

Drawing inspiration from the mechanism of a noose, the hangman technique involves the creation of a loop that is then maneuvered around the filter's hook or apex. This loop acts as a leverage point, allowing for the application of controlled force to disengage the filter from its endothelialized or embedded position. The hangman technique is particularly effective in retrieving filters that are difficult to access with traditional snaring methods due to their orientation or embedment.^[6] Its approach provides a unique solution to complex retrieval scenarios, enhancing success rates in otherwise challenging cases. The difference between the hangman technique and the loop over snare technique lies in the fact that the

guide wire instead of being placed underneath the apex as in the loop over the snare technique is placed between the tilted apex of the IVC filter and the wall of the vena cava, the loop is then used to pull and tease the endothelial tissue around the apex of the filter and the wall of the inferior vena cava to free the incorporated apex and allow for access to the IVC filter hook with a traditional intravascular snare.

6. Endobronchial Forceps Use

Adapting tools from bronchoscopy, the use of endobronchial forceps for IVC filter retrieval represents a cross-disciplinary innovation. These forceps allow for the direct grasping of the filter, offering a tactile and precise control over its extraction.^[7] This method is especially beneficial for filters that are deeply embedded, tilted, or have significant tissue ingrowth, where other techniques may struggle to achieve a secure engagement. The tactile feedback and mechanical advantage provided by endobronchial forceps can significantly improve the success rates of complex retrievals, making it a valuable technique in difficult cases. The endobronchial forceps most often utilized in this application are semi rigid 1.5 and 3mm alligator jaw forceps. These four steps traditionally transition through sheaths between 14 and 16 French. The semi rigid forceps are preferable as a slight bend can be placed along the shaft of the forceps making them steerable under fluoroscopy so that they can be guided to the wall of the inferior vena cava to engage filters that are tilted with their apex against the inferior vena cava wall. The technique involves gentle manipulation and denuding of endothelial overgrowth encasing the apex of the IVC filter. Once the excessive tissue overgrowth is removed, the apex is liberated from the wall in traditional snare retrieval techniques can be employed to retrieve the filter. A caveat to this technique is that at this time there is no brand of endobronchial forceps that has an on label application for use for IVC filter retrieval or intravascular foreign body removal.

7. Phillips CAVA Clear for Retrieval

The Phillips CAVA Clear system is designed specifically for the mechanical disruption of tissue ingrowth around an IVC filter, facilitating its release and subsequent retrieval^[8]. This tool represents a targeted approach to overcoming one of the significant challenges in filter retrieval - endothelialization. By directly addressing the issue of tissue incorporation, the Phillips CAVA Clear system enhances the likelihood of successful retrieval, offering a novel solution in the toolbox for managing complex filter retrievals. The Phillips CavaClear Laser Sheath device is designed for the removal of embedded

filters. It utilizes ultraviolet laser radiation via a laser filament circumferentially embedded around the tip of the laser sheath to facilitate the detachment of firmly adherent IVC filters from the IVC wall, making it a significant advancement for cases where filters are difficult to retrieve due to embedding in the vascular wall or tissue ingrowth. The device operates by employing circumferential tissue ablation, allowing for the efficient capture of the filter within seconds of laser activation. This mechanism not only enhances the efficacy of removal procedures but also minimizes the force required for retrieval compared to standard techniques. Clinical studies have supported the use of the CavaClear Laser Sheath, demonstrating its safety and effectiveness. The device has shown a high procedural technical success rate of 96% with a major adverse event rate ranging from 0.7% to 2%.[8] It has been noted for its capability to provide a solution for the removal of chronically embedded IVC filters, which previously had limited removal options.

8. Purpose-Built Sheath Systems

Purpose-built sheath systems, such as the Argon Medical Kodiak sheath, are engineered to cater to the specific challenges of complex IVC filter retrievals. These sheaths offer enhanced maneuverability and are compatible with a variety of filter types, enabling their effective engagement and retrieval. The development of such sheath systems represents a significant advancement in the field, providing interventional radiologists with the means to approach complex retrievals. The Kodiak Dual Port Coaxial Introducer Kit features a large-bore sheath and a Y-shaped adapter. This allows physicians to introduce several components simultaneously through a single access site, simplifying complex procedures where a robust device is required for efficient treatment delivery. This kit is specifically engineered to introduce therapeutic or diagnostic devices into the vasculature, streamlining complex vascular procedures. Its unique features include hemostasis valves within the Y-Connector and sheaths that prevent bleed-back and minimize blood loss, whether used as a single sheath or as a coaxial system. The Y-connector facilitates the simultaneous introduction of multiple components, easily scaling from simple to complex applications while maintaining hemostasis. Additionally, the kit includes embedded RO bands for enhanced fluoroscopic visualization, twist-lock connections for secure coaxial system assembly, large-bore sheaths for introducing larger devices, and braided sheaths that provide optimal rigidity, supporting device integrity and preventing kinking. The system includes a 14F x 53cm inner sheath, a 16F x 45cm outer sheath, and a 14F x 61cm dilator assembly.

9. Filter Inversion Utilizing Large-Bore Sheaths

Employing large-bore sheaths, such as the 20-22 French Medtronic Sentrant or Gore Dry Seal sheaths, for filter inversion is a technique that radically diverges from conventional retrieval methods. This approach involves inverting the filter within the large sheath to facilitate its extraction, a method that can be particularly useful in cases where traditional approaches are ineffective. Filter inversion techniques address the challenges of tightly adherent or anatomically unfavorable filter placements, offering an innovative solution that can enhance the success rates of complex retrievals. This technique, as with all techniques, should be approached with caution and should be limited to use on nitinol IVC filter as the technique involves using forceps from femoral vein access to grab a hold of the IVC filter below the apex and literally bending the filter back until the filter inverts and can be folded up into a large bore sheath. This technique has been described in clinical literature but its application to date has been limited to certain institutions with robust filter retrieval programs that have a specific comfort level in employing graduated and advanced techniques.

10. Discussion

The evolution of techniques and tools for the retrieval of inferior vena cava (IVC) filters has ushered in a new era in image guided procedures, challenging the traditional definitions of "complex" retrievals. ^[1]This shift not only highlights the field's innovation but also underscores the necessity for a nuanced understanding and approach towards managing patients with difficult-to-retrieve IVC filters. The development and integration of advanced progressive techniques, such as the loop-over-snare, balloon inflation, hangman technique, endobronchial forceps use, Philips CAVA Clear device, purpose-built sheath systems like the Argon Medical's Kodiak sheath, and filter inversion utilizing large-bore sheaths, have significantly expanded the procedural arsenal available to physician's and clinicians. These innovations offer the potential for improved patient outcomes, especially in scenarios that were previously considered challenging or even infeasible. Each of these advanced techniques brings its own set of advantages, addressing specific challenges associated with IVC filter retrievals. For instance, techniques that provide greater control and precision, such as the loop-over-snare or the use of endobronchial forceps, may be particularly beneficial in cases of deeply embedded or tilted filters. Meanwhile, methods that facilitate the disruption of tissue ingrowth around the filter, like the Philips CAVA Clear device, represent a significant step forward in managing filters that have become integrated into the venous wall over time. Similarly, large-bore sheath systems, including the Argon Medical Kodiak

sheath, offer new possibilities for managing a variety of filter types and retrieval complexities, further illustrating the dynamic nature of the field.

As the adoption of these techniques becomes more widespread, there is a pressing need for standardization and comprehensive outcome assessment. This involves not only the establishment of guidelines and protocols to ensure the safe and effective application of these techniques but also the continuous evaluation of procedural outcomes through multicenter studies and registries. Such efforts are crucial for validating the efficacy of new tools and techniques, identifying best practices, and ultimately, ensuring the highest standards of patient care.

Moreover, the collaboration among interventional physicians, medical device manufacturers, and regulatory bodies is essential for driving innovation, facilitating the exchange of knowledge and expertise, and developing training programs to equip clinicians with the necessary skills to perform these advanced procedures. Additionally, patient education plays a pivotal role in this evolving landscape, as informed patients are better positioned to engage in shared decision-making processes regarding their treatment options. The redefinition of "complex" IVC filter retrieval reflects not only the technological and procedural advancements in the field but also the broader shift towards more patient-centered, innovative, and evidence-based practices in invasive, image guided medicine. As we move forward, it is imperative that the community continues to embrace these changes through ongoing research, education, and collaboration, ensuring that these advancements are translated into improved outcomes for patients across the globe. For accurate, up-to-date information and guidelines on these techniques, consulting peer-reviewed journals, professional society guidelines, and official medical device documentation is recommended. Robust monitoring and progressive filter retrieval programs will continue to be a part of the treatment algorithm for PE prevention for patients where IVC filtration is clearly indicated based on societal guideline recommendations. As such, understanding the nuances a procedural progression in the panacea of retrieval techniques is an important skill set to master for physicians who place and retrieve IVC filters.

11. Conclusions

The evolving landscape of inferior vena cava (IVC) filter retrieval marks a significant departure from the traditional dichotomy of complex versus non-complex procedures. This reevaluation stems from a growing recognition within the medical community that nearly all IVC filters can be removed with a high rate of success, given the right combination of techniques tailored to address the specific challenges each case presents. The literature

increasingly supports the notion that, with advancements in retrieval technologies and methodologies, the decision to remove an IVC filter should not hinge on a binary classification of complexity but rather on a nuanced understanding of the unique circumstances surrounding each filter and patient. The variables influencing filter retrieval are as diverse as the patient populations we serve. Factors such as the positioning of the filter apex within the IVC, the duration for which the filter has been in place, and the degree of filter integration into the venous wall are critical considerations that inform the choice of retrieval technique. This personalized approach underscores the importance of treating each retrieval as a distinct entity, necessitating a bespoke plan that considers the individual situational parameters of each patient and filter.

Moving beyond the simplistic labels of complex and non-complex allows for a more flexible, informed, and patient-centric approach to IVC filter retrieval. It acknowledges the reality that each retrieval scenario is unique and demands a strategic application of the diverse techniques at our disposal. From the loop-over-snare to the use of cutting-edge devices like the Philips CAVA Clear, and from the deployment of purpose-built sheath systems to innovative, situational methods like filter inversion, the array of available strategies enables trained physicians to navigate the intricacies of each case with precision and confidence.

This shift towards a more adaptive and tailored approach to IVC filter retrieval is not just a theoretical ideal but a practical necessity. It challenges the field to continually refine and expand its technical repertoire, engage in rigorous outcome assessment, and foster an environment of continuous learning and adaptation. Moreover, it calls for a collaborative effort to standardize these advanced techniques, ensuring that they are accessible and comprehensible to practitioners across the spectrum of interventional radiology.

In conclusion, the journey of IVC filter retrieval from a rigid classification of complexity to a more fluid and dynamic understanding is emblematic of the broader evolution within image guided interventions. It reflects a commitment to advancing patient care through innovation, precision, and a deep respect for the unique needs of each individual. As we move forward, the continued development and dissemination of knowledge, techniques, and best practices will be paramount in ensuring that all patients benefit from the highest standards of care, irrespective of the challenges their particular cases may present.

12. References

[1] C. Molvar. "Inferior Vena Cava Filtration in the Management of Venous Thromboembolism: Filtering the Data". *Seminars in Interventional Radiology*. vol. 29. no. 03.

pp. 204-217. Oct. 2012. 10.1055/s-0032-1326931.

[2] "Inferior Vena Cava Filters: Placement and Retrieval".

[3] K. Barsoum, N. Kethidi, P. A. Shukla and A. Kumar. "Abstract No. 535 Safety and efficacy of complex inferior vena cava filter retrievals: a systematic review". *Journal of Vascular and Interventional Radiology*. vol. 32. no. 5. pp. S145-S145. May. 2021. 10.1016/j.jvir.2021.03.344.

[4] G. Kuyumcu and T. Walker. "Inferior vena cava filter retrievals, standard and novel techniques". *Cardiovascular diagnosis and therapy*. vol. 6. no. 6. pp. 642-650. Dec. 2016. 10.21037/cdt.2016.09.07.[5] K. Desai et al.. "Retrievable IVC Filters: Comprehensive Review of Device-related Complications and Advanced Retrieval Techniques". *Radiographics*. vol. 37. no. 4. pp. 1236-1245. Jul. 2017. 10.1148/rg.2017160167.

[6] B. Iliescu and Z. J. Haskal. "Advanced Techniques for Removal of Retrievable Inferior Vena Cava Filters". *CardioVascular and Interventional Radiology*. vol. 35. no. 4. pp. 741-750. Jun. 2011. 10.1007/s00270-011-0205-z.

[7] J. L. Laws, R. J. Lewandowski, R. K. Ryu and K. Desai. "Retrieval of Inferior Vena Cava Filters: Technical Considerations". *Seminars in Interventional Radiology*. vol. 33. no. 02. pp. 144-148. May. 2016. 10.1055/s-0036-1582119.

[8] Kuo, W. et al. Laser-Assisted Removal of Embedded Vena Cava Filters: A First-In-Human Escalation Trial in 500 Patients Refractory to High-Force Retrieval. *Journal of the American Heart Association* 9:24, 1-9 (2020).

1. Loop Over Snare

Figure 1: Loop Over Snare

2. Kodiak Set

3. Cava Clear

4. Forceps

Figure 2: Kodiak Introducer

Figure 3: Cava Clear

Figure 4: Forceps Retrieval